

IMPROVED CASH FLOW STATEMENTS

Dzhuliyev Jamshid Olim

student of the Banking and Finance Academy of the Republic of Uzbekistan
Faculty Master banking accounting, auditing and control .

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Abstract: this article discusses the issues of improving the preparation of cash flow statements

Key words: finance, capital, reports, profit, movements, shareholding, credits.

The statement of changes in equity records the changes that occurred during the reporting period in the capital of the organization, including the total newly invested (reinvested) profit, showing only those transactions that affected the capital, we can argue that the cash flow statement is an integral part of the Statement. After all, it is he who gives users information about the sufficiency of free cash to pay dividends to shareholders, the possibility of repaying accounts payable, what financial or investment activities the organization undertook during the reporting period, about fixed assets acquired by the company over the period, the dynamics and causes of changes in accounts payable, new issues shares and the direction of the received funds. That is why, in our opinion, the statement of cash flows makes an exceptional wave.

Economists express clear points of view on how important it is. So, for example, L. A. Bernstein notes the growing interest in the cash flow statement due to the fact that other forms of reporting are compiled on an accumulative basis, which means they will be less useful to the user, wishing to track changes in the organization's cash flow [63, p. 332]. The same opinion is expressed by Y. Brigham and J. Houston, who argue that the company's cash flow will differ from profit, since not all types of profit listed in the income statement lead to the payment of money [68, p. 73]. Many Russian economists adhere to a similar point of view. In particular, E. N. Dombrovskaya emphasizes that the analysis of cash flows does not have restrictions that depend on the indicators of other reporting forms and on the accounting policy applied by the organization [80, p. 142]. Similarly, S. È. Korenkova says that profit is a "paper" indicator, which will only matter if it is confirmed by the corresponding amount of money, calculated according to the principle of real execution [91, p. 155]. Thus, the possibility of reflecting the real solvency of the company, and not profit "on paper", is noted by many economists as one of the main features of the cash flow statement. We cannot but agree with such a position. Indeed, the leading place in the system of indicators of the company's financial condition traditionally occupies Really However, profit is not a guarantee of the company's solvency. So, according to

accounting data, an enterprise that is profitable can become bankrupt due to the inability to fulfill payment obligations on time and in the required quantity. At the same time, a loss-making enterprise can "survive" at the expense of available free money. Therefore, despite the fact that the main goal of managing any commercial organization is to make a profit, we believe that in addition to profitability, an important factor for an organization is to achieve a certain cash balance.

Many com mecon. Despite the fact that the acute part of the crisis has passed, it is not possible to state the fact of the complete recovery of the world economy as a whole, and the Russian economy in particular, from the crisis even today. It is even difficult to predict the time for overcoming the crisis in the coming years. In light of this, in our opinion, financial stability and financial stability, and therefore, the sources of information about these indicators, that is, reporting in terms of cash flows, and the mechanisms for their evaluation, are of key importance for economic development. Based on the foregoing, namely the report on the movement of cash neg Therefore, in this work, we consider the possibility of increasing the information content of this report.

The ability to reflect the indicators of cash in the Statements in dynamics, and not in statics, as one of the key features, is highlighted by another group of economists. So, N. n. Ilysheva argues that it is the financial dynamics of a commercial enterprise that should be considered as a certain link between its static financial positions at the beginning and end of the period. It determines the way of transition from the original with regalo 4]. n. P. Shishkina [126] and E. M. Sorokina [147] talk about the possibility of showing the innovative movement of cash deposits otim. We also consider it important to note the "dynamic" function of this report. The balance sheet reflects the principal's cash average at a specific time point (n. The cash flow statement, in turn, reflects the dynamics of the money averages. Due to the fact that the cash flow statement reflects cash indicators in dynamics and is a link between one static financial condition and subsequent, Reporting should be considered only if it is possible to compare the data of the balance sheet and the cash flow statement. Therefore, in this work, an important place is assigned to inenock copossetro nn poitel idea. This issue is discussed in detail in the second and third chapters of this dissertation research.

agree that one of the key features of the cash flow statement is the ability to show not only the direction of cash flows (inflow / outflow), but also what types of company activities led to this (current, investment or financial) many

economists. A similar point of view is shared by such scientists as M. A. Vakhrushina, who notes that the cash flow statement allows you to see "in what volume and from what sources the funds were received, the directions of their use" [72, p. 216]. A. Ä. Sheremet says that "the grouping of cash flows by type of activity makes it possible to reflect the impact of each type on cash" [125, p. 76]. A similar point of view is supported by foreign economists, such as the above-mentioned L. A. Bernstein [63] and V. J. Love [95]. We agree that one of the main features of the cash flow statement that needs to be considered is that this report shows not only the direction of cash flows (inflow / outflow), but what exactly the company's activity contributed to this, allowing the financial analyst to obtain information.

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